

Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management: An Overview

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Abstract:

Working at office and social interaction with employees is essential. But after the COVID pandemic period various work of the organizations are happening online through various modes such as google meet, zoom, Microsoft teams etc. Various work, decisions related to work are doing through online mode increasing the efficiency, transparency with minimum time. Technology is developing day by day and use of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management is helping to do various HR functions such as recruitment, selection, training and development, orientation to the employees and measuring employees work performance by the technique of performance appraisal of employees. In this research paper, significance of AI in HRM is studied along with various opportunities and challenges to operate Artificial Intelligence in the system. This research article is concluded that use of AI is essential in HR functions because scrutiny of application for the recruitment, providing prompt feedback to the candidates, selection of best candidate for the organization, providing orientation, training and development opportunities, reviewing the employees performance by keeping transparency in the system and finally for taking strategic decisions for the organization

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Human Resource Management, role of AI in HRM, Opportunities of AI in HRM, challenges of AI in HRM*

Introduction:

Traditional human resource function require more time and there is possibility of inaccuracy in work. But with help of Artificial intelligence accuracy increases. Transferring, converting and transforming the traditional Human resource functions into computerized term is known as Artificial intelligence in human resource management and this is possible through application and using the AI techniques to HR processes and various HR functions. “Artificial intelligence means using various machine learning models, automation system, algorithm system to various functions of HR that fasten the work of HR in computerized manner”. Employees efficiency and experiences are becoming upgrade through the use of automatic system like Artificial intelligence. This upgrading system improves

employees performance and system accuracy to perform various HR related functions. Artificial intelligence means giving and providing the automatic brain to the computer to perform various HR related functions and various jobs or responsibilities like studying, acquiring the knowledge, problems solving, understanding and identifying various patterns of the system, and languages. And performing these different types of tasks related to HR functions, there is a requirement of human intelligence and all the work can be done with help of computers and various smart and updated work and activities can be done with help of AI. With help of experts, these expertise in system, giving input to the system of computer is possible and then that computerized system help to search different data into the computers with a few seconds. Various

cognitive and thoughtful functions like learning, studying, observation, providing opinion,, problems solving, analysis, calculative and analytical data is provided by the Artificial intelligence. We can say that various function in various sectors Artificial intelligence can do. Artificial intelligence in human resource management play very significant role that enhances employees capabilities, efficiency. “AI ability of machine to learn, analyze, interpret, understand the on their own way same as the human being think and do”. AI in HRM helps to do various HR functions that reduces times and increases efficiency to work and to attract good talent to the organization.

Literature Review:

1. Dr. Priya (2021) in her research paper” explained the importance of Artificial intelligence in HRM and also focused that various HR functions can be facilitated with help of AI very efficiently with very less time and effectively. She also studied various HR functions and its relations with AI and AI capabilities to perform the HR functions like a human being to achieve organizational goals and also that helps to take proper decisions and form various organsational related strategies that helps to the organization to manage the employees efficiency in the organization.
2. Dr. Owais Ahmed (2018) studied in his research paper Artificial intelligence in HR by studying and applying AI system in a computerized manner in human resource functions. Various HR functions, its importance and essentiality of AI is studied that help to improve employees work efficiency and work accuracy. They also observed that AI system provides multiple solutions to the HR managers to perform the HR functions.

3. Kaur Mandeep., et. al. (2023) Studied various AI driven HRM systems and processes that have made various big changes into the HRM functions into the AI system that boost employees performance. Various HR functions such as recruitments, form screening, performance appraisal, problem solving can be done with the help of AI technology, employees retention. These AI driven HR system enhances organizational work performance, efficiency, identify the trend, employees model, employees needs, employees satisfaction, its analysis, proper decision making etc that finally help to the organization to achieve organizational goals and objectives.

Objectives of Study:

- 1) To study the concept of Artificial Intelligence and Human Resource Management
- 2) To study the significant role of Artificial Intelligence in Human resource management functions
- 3) To study the various opportunities of Artificial Intelligence in Human resource management
- 4) To study challenges faced while using the AI in HRM

Research Methodology:

The data for this research purpose is collected by using secondary data sources such as books, magazines, research papers, newspapers, shodhaganga website, internet, thesis, articles etc. The method for this research paper is used qualitative research method and all the data is collected with help of secondary sources.

Role of AI in Human Resource Management: HRM:

Employees are the assets of the company. Human resource is the most important part and

asset of the every business organizations. Hence, screening the applications from the candidates, attracting the best candidates, recruitment, selection of best candidates, retaining the best qualified employees, providing training and development opportunities, performance appraisal of the employees, reviewing employees performance is main functions of Human Resource Management. Attracting the best and retaining the best qualified candidates and also optimizing and optimum utilization of human resources the main theme of HRM. And the organizations which are taking more efforts for the employees that achieve its objectives for the long period of time in the market.

Artificial Intelligence:

Today is the era of modern era. In today's generation use of computer software and updated technology, internet is essential for fast answers. Various computerized system such as chat GPT, google, copilot, Gemini, meta AI are used for prompt work with less time and for smooth, effective functioning of operations in the organizations. Various organizations are using skilled computer technology, machine learning, algorithm system for their operations in the organizations. Skilled and talented employees are hired by the organization to handle and to make the system computerized and to make the various operations intelligent with proper technologies. Artificial intelligence in human resource management play very significant role that improves employees capabilities, efficiency. "AI ability of machine to learn, analyze, interpret, understand the on their own way same as the human being think and do".

Significance / Importance of Artificial Intelligence in HRM Functions:

Today is the age of internet and various work can be done with help of computerized

network that fasten the work very efficiently with very less time. Efficient and skilled employees can be recruited to develop this artificial intelligence functions. Various operation in various sectors, AI is useful. In HRM, AI perform very significant role such as:

Recruitment and Selection:

Recruitment means attracting best candidate for the organization by matching organizational requirement and employees skill and qualification. In the recruitment, screening of employees applications can be done by HR department in the organization. But this require more time to proceed. For the smooth and fast functioning of recruitment, fast screening of applications, to assist the candidates to make fast enquiries, Artificial intelligence technology is essential. Selection means selecting the best qualified and experience candidate that match between organizational requirement and employees skill to do that work. AI help to track best qualified candidate for the organization. Hence for this fast work AI is useful that make the recruitment and selection process very efficiently, effectively with very less time that facilitates to the organizations as well as employees also.

Training and Development:

Training the art of increasing the knowledge and skill of employees. This training and developmental programs can be conducted by the organizations on online platform by using Internet, zoom, google meet that reduces the employees and organizational time, cost and provides training to the employees. AI provides these facilities very efficiently with very less time and cost all over the globe.

Performance Appraisal:

Performance appraisal means measurement and reviewing the employees performance that system is require more time. But with help of Artificial intelligence, these reviewing system work become smoothly, fasten and employees can feed their every data into the system and employer also take review very effectively with very low time and promptly.

Benefits of AI in HRM:

- 1) AI facilitates HR team in its various work such screening and assessment of resume, managing employees salary and compensation, arranging the meeting etc. This increases efficiency, accuracy and make the team more productive and strategic.
- 2) Candidates can prepare their resume and can make preparation for the interview by asking the questions to the AI and matching of candidates skill with organizational requirement is possible by using AI
- 3) AI powered chatbots help to the HR managers to assists employees to solve their queries, develop the efficiency and skills, performance and provides the feedback quickly and efficiently.
- 4) Better employees engagement is possible by using AI technology because it help to draft communications with employees, to frame various company related updated news or letter, up to date in policy of the organization, reward structure and different programs that make employees more participative to the system.
- 5) AI help to make strategic decision making and its proper and effective feedback into the system.
- 6) Most of the HR managers do not get talented workforce and can not fill the proper roles. But with help of AI, organization get talented employees.

- 7) AI make recruitment process more efficient by assessing employees responses and by drafting job specification and job description that improves employees work performance and productivity.

Risks or Challenges of AI in HRM:

1. HR managers depends on AI system and its algorithm but if feeding of algorithm by experts is in accurate or biased then there is possibility of inaccurate results and inaccurate decisions
2. AI use the data without the consent or permission of user that distract and harm the privacy of data that may be available to all in the organization without the permission of user.
3. HR managers depends on AI system that make overdependence of employees on AI system that may reduce the human knowledge and behavior to think and to take decisions.
4. Most of the employees that is more than 80% employees need the knowledge of AI and its operation but they are not skilled or expert in this field.
5. Most of the HR team and employees are showing their unwillingness and unenthusiastic to adopt the AI system because of fear to lose their job when it is replacing by the AI system.
6. Some decisions of AI are not matched with human decisions. Hence HR team do not consider AI data.
7. Handling of AI system required more updated, trained and qualified employees. Getting qualified candidate and retaining them is a big challenge for the organizations.

Conclusion:

Humans are the assets of the company or any organization and its selection and development is most important thing to survive in

the competition for every organization. AI in HRM helps to do various HR functions that reduces times and increases efficiency to work and to attract good talent to the organization. AI help to increase employees work performance, efficiency, productivity and finally to achieve organizational goals. AI help to make strategic decisions that make organizational improvement by motivating employees. But it is not always possible because all the decisions that generated by the AI system are not always accurate because of biased algorithm that have feed in AI system. Sometimes algorithm that have provided in the system is biased that may create inaccurate decision that harm to the organization and employees are not ready to operate that because of insufficient knowledge to handle it. Hence, use of AI is essential by the organizations but appointment of right and knowledgeable candidate and providing the training and development to employees is essential to operate AI system.

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